

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of *p*-Bromo Mandelic Acid(*p*-BMA) by Potassium Peroxydisulphate

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The kinetics of uncatalysed oxidation of *p*-Bromo Mandelic Acid (*p*-BMA) by peroxydisulphate ion in aqueous medium has been investigated. The reaction is found to be first order w. r. t. $S_2O_8^{2-}$ ion, zero order w. r. t. *p*-BMA, but the specific rate increases with an increase in $S_2O_8^{2-}$ or *p*-BMA concentration. H^+ ion exerts a specific inhibitory effect on the rate. The specific inhibitory effect of various ions on the rate is in the order.

The temperature coefficient, energy of activation, frequency factor and entropy of activation have been determined. The complete oxidation of one mole of *p*-Bromo Mandelic Acid required one mole of Potassium peroxydisulphate and the final product of oxidation is *p*-Bromo benzaldehyde. On the basis of these kinetic results a suitable reaction mechanism has been proposed and the corresponding rate equation derived.

IN the oxidation of α -hydroxy acids by different oxidising agents¹⁻⁶ the α -C-H bond cleavage has been reported in the formation of oxidation products. It was felt that mandelic acid by $S_2O_8^{2-}$ could explain the effect of substituent groups in the *p*-position in the benzene ring on the rate of oxidation. A systematic study of the oxidation of substituted mandelic acids by $S_2O_8^{2-}$ ion is being undertaken to establish the effect of the substituent groups and the cleavage of α -C-H bond in oxidation process. The present paper deals with the kinetic results obtained for uncatalysed oxidation of *p*-Bromo Mandelic Acid by $S_2O_8^{2-}$ ion.

Materials and Methods :

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and the experimental technique followed was similar to that described earlier⁷.

Results

Kinetic runs were carried out at 35° unless otherwise specified. It may be pointed out that the thermal decomposition of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ ion up to a temperature of 45° is negligible. The typical kinetic runs at different concentrations of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ ion and in presence of K_2SO_4 are represented in Fig. 1 and tabulated in Table 1. The K_2SO_4 is taken to keep the ionic strength and K^+ ion concentration constant, because K^+ ion has inhibitory effect on the specific rate (vide Table 4).

Fig. 1. Effect of $K_2S_2O_8$ conc. [*P*-BMA] = $2.712 \times 10^{-3} M$
Temp. = 35°

An examination of the data shows that first order rate constant calculated from the initial rate ($-dc/dt$) w.r.t. $S_2O_8^{2-}$ using differential method comes out to be unity. The specific rate increases with an increase in $S_2O_8^{2-}$ ion concentration and follows the expression :

$$\log k = -3.64 + 38.88[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0$$

TABLE-1

[p-BMA] = 2.721 × 10 ⁻³ M		Temp. = 35°	
K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ × 10 ³ M	K ₂ SO ₄ × 10 ² M	-dc/dt × 10 ³	k × 10 ⁴ min ⁻¹
0.5	4.5	1.59	3.48
1.0	4.0	3.16	5.75
1.5	3.5	4.58	9.21
2.0	3.0	6.04	13.54

Effect of p-BMA :

To study the effect of p-BMA concentration on the rate, the reaction was carried out at different concentrations of the p-BMA (Table-2).

TABLE-2

[K ₂ S ₂ O ₈] = 0.5 × 10 ⁻² M		Temp. = 35°			
[p-BMA] × 10 ³ M	1.356	2.712	4.068	5.424	6.780
k × 10 ³	0.96	1.439	1.77	2.42	3.07

It is clear that the rate constant increases with an increase in concentration of the p-BMA and follows the same nature⁷⁻⁸ expression :

$$k = 0.25 \times 10^{-8} + 0.42[p-BMA]_0.$$

The order w.r.t. p-BMA or calculation by differential method comes out to be a very small fraction which is negligible and has been considered to be zero as in our other studies⁷⁻⁸.

Effect of H⁺ Ion :

To study the effect of H⁺ ion on the rate of reaction the experiments were carried out in presence of large concentration of K₂SO₄ (vide Table 3).

TABLE-3

[p-BMA] = 2.712 × 10 ⁻³ M		Temp. = 35°			
[K ₂ SO ₄] = 0.1 M, [K ₂ S ₂ O ₈] = 0.5 × 10 ⁻² M					
[H ₂ SO ₄] 10 ³ × M	0.00	0.1	0.5	1.0	
k × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	0.303	0.287	0.255	0.164	

It is clear that the increase in H⁺ ion concentration decreases the rate of reaction suggesting that H⁺ ion have inhibitory effect on the rate of reaction, similar to that S₂O₈²⁻ ion oxidation⁷ reaction.

Salt Effect and Specific Effect of Ions :

The salt effect on the reaction studied using potassium sulphate was found to be negative and primary exponential type. The specific effects of various ions have been investigated at constant ionic strength. The results of these studies are given in Table 4.

TABLE-4

[K ₂ S ₂ O ₈] = 0.5 × 10 ⁻² M		Temp. = 35°	
[p-BMA] = 2.712 × 10 ⁻³ M			
Cations added	Conc. (M)	ks × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	(k - ks) × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
-	-	1.439	0.000
K ₂ SO ₄	0.033	0.575	0.864
Na ₂ SO ₄	0.033	0.858	0.586
Li ₂ SO ₄	0.033	0.921	0.518
ZnSO ₄	0.025	0.959	0.480
MgSO ₄	0.025	1.096	0.345
Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	0.066	1.151	0.288

The above data shows that the inhibitory effect of various ions is in the order.

and a plot of (k - ks) vs ionic radius (r.A°) is linear and follows the relationship (Fig. 2.)

$$(k - ks) = 0.00023 + 0.675 \times 10^5(r)$$

Fig. 2.

The above linear relationship clearly indicates that with the increase in the ionic radius (Angstroms units) of the inhibitory ion, the chances of reaction between reductant and oxidant decrease and consequently lowering of the rate as observed experimentally.

TABLE-5

Temp. K°	$K \times 10^3$ min^{-1}	Temp. coefficient	Energy of activation (ΔE) in Kcals mole^{-1}	Frequency factor lit. $\text{mole}^{-1} \text{sec.}^{-1}$ $A \times 10^{-6}$	Entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) a.u.	Free energy (ΔG) K cals mole^{-1}
308	0.9212			3.767	-30.27	24.19
308	1.439	2.27	15.46	3.714	-30.28	24.57
313	2.093	2.28	16.10	3.652	29.66	24.74
318	3.290			3.793	-30.26	24.86
	Mean	2.275	15.78	3.731	-30.142	24.59

(ΔH^\ddagger) = 15.25 K cal mole^{-1} (Graphically)

Effect of Temperature :

Table 5 gives the value of energy parameters for the reactions.

ΔH^\ddagger has been calculated by a plot of $\log(k/kT/h)$ vs. $1/T$ on the basis of the equation $k = kT/h \cdot e^{-\Delta H^\ddagger/RT} \times e^{\Delta S^\ddagger/R}$. The value of ΔH^\ddagger (15.25 K cal. mole^{-1}) has been used in the above equation to calculate ΔS^\ddagger .

Mole Ratio and Analysis of Products :

The mole ratio of $K_2S_2O_8$ and *p*-BMA comes out to be unity. The oxidation product was isolated from the concentrated mixture of reductant and oxidant containing as excess of reductant. On keeping at 45° for overnight the reaction product *p*-Bromo benzaldehyde precipitates, which after recrystallisation melts at 58°. Its IR spectrum confirms it to be *p*-Bromo benzaldehyde.

Discussion

The first order w.r.t. $S_2O_8^{2-}$, zero order w.r.t. *p*-BMA, the strong inhibitory effect of the potassium ion, the increase of specific rate with an increase in *p*-BMA and $K_2S_2O_8$ concentration, show that this reaction is very much similar to the uncatalysed oxidation of thiosulphate ion⁹⁻¹⁰ by peroxydisulphate ion. These similarities in kinetic behaviour together with the fact that the mole ratio is one lead to the conclusion that the following mechanism may be operative.

The first two steps have been suggested by Bartlett and Cotman¹¹ in other uncatalysed oxidation by peroxydisulphate ion. The experimental

evidence for sulphate free radical has already been observed in the polymerisation studies¹²⁻¹⁶ using peroxydisulphate labelled. S^{35} as an initiator and the existence of hydroxyl free radical has also been reported¹⁷. Applying the steady state treatment to the radicals SO_4^- , $\cdot OH$ and $\cdot COOH$ and making the necessary approximations the rate expression comes out to be :

$$-\frac{d[S_2O_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k[S_2O_8^{2-}]$$

This is in agreement with the experimental results and here k is first-order rate constant.

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